

Use Cases for the PROMISCES Decision Support Framework (DSF)

Real-world examples of how the PROMISCES DSF supports risk assessment, monitoring, prevention, and strategy creation for PM(T) substances.

<https://promisces.eu/Results/Tools/PROMISCES+DSF.html>

PROMISCES has developed use cases for each of the modules included in the PROMISCES DSF in order to demonstrate to end-users – whether water operators, chemical industry actors or policymakers – how the DSF can be used to address questions related to the management of persistent (P), mobile (M), and potentially toxic ((T); PM(T)) substances.

Printable index card versions of the DSF use cases, to be used at events and workshops, can be found on pages 4-7 of this document.

DSF Module: PMT Assessment

Problem: An industrial site is requesting a permit for discharging wastewater containing unregulated substances, such as 1,4-dioxane. Authorities need to assess the permit request to protect the receiving water body.

Solution: Using **PMT Assessment**, search for 1,4-dioxane to obtain information on its P, M and T characteristics, as well as the other substances.

How the PROMISCES DSF helps: The **PMT Assessment** module verifies the persistence, mobility, and toxicity of substances, helping regulators evaluate potential hazardous chemicals in industrial discharges, for example. Additionally, see Recommendation No. 1 in Deliverable D5.8 in the *Strategy Creation* module.

DSF Module: Diagnosis

Problem: A water utility is updating their PFAS monitoring strategy but is worried that key hazardous substances are missing.

Solution: Use **Diagnosis** to check the monitored chemicals, such as perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA), and find structurally similar ones with equal or greater PM(T) risk. Then, use *Search Substances* for more details on these chemicals.

How the PROMISCES DSF helps: The **Diagnosis** module presents the 30 most structurally similar substances to a given search query, allowing the user to examine alternatives based on P, M, T weightings.

DSF Module: Solution Assessment – Prevention

Problem: A chemical company's wastewater treatment plant detected diethyl phthalate (DEP) in their sludge. They want to prevent its release in future cycles but aren't sure how to replace it.

Solution: Using the **Solution Assessment – Prevention** module, look through the various databases in *Question 3* to find substitutes for DEP.

How the PROMISCES DSF helps: The **Prevention** module identifies where a substance is used and suggests safer alternatives or non-substitution measures like BATs or SSbD. A link to the *PMT Assessment* module helps to identify whether the substance has P, M or T characteristics.

DSF Module: Solution Assessment – Monitoring

Problem: A regional water authority suspects that a local river is contaminated with PM(T) substances but is unsure which pollutants to monitor and how to design an effective monitoring program.

Solution: In **Solution Assessment – Monitoring**, filter on river water matrix in *Question 1* to obtain data on occurrences and frequencies of relevant substances.

How the PROMISCES DSF helps: The **Solution Assessment – Monitoring module** provides a visual overview and downloadable on frequently monitored substances, their average concentration, levels in different matrices and detection frequency, helping decision-makers identify substances for treatment or monitoring programs.

DSF Module: Solution Assessment – Risk Assessment

Problem: A municipality plans to reuse treated wastewater for irrigation but is unsure if PFOS levels pose a risk to human health.

Solution: Use *Question 1* in **Solution Assessment – Risk Assessment** to derive a groundwater threshold for PFOS: $\Sigma\text{PFAS } 24 = 0.0044 \mu\text{g/L}$; assume PFOS RPF = 2 \rightarrow threshold = $-2.66 \mu\text{g/L}$ (\log_{10}). *Question 2* shows PFOS is often detected above this threshold in wastewater, indicating potential risk.

How the PROMISCES DSF helps: The **Solution Assessment – Risk Assessment** module compiles information on regulatory limits and health-based guideline values and provides PROMISCES-developed models to assist decision makers in implementing safe wastewater reuse.

DSF Module: Solution Assessment – Treatment

Problem: A water utility is considering a semi-closed water cycle to improve drinking water supply but needs to ensure that it can effectively remove PM(T) substances, including PFAS.

Solution: Select Route A in the **Solution Assessment – Treatment** module to explore treatment technologies tested for a semi-closed water cycle and a set of target PM(T) substances.

How the PROMISCES DSF helps: The **Solution Assessment –Treatment** module provides guidance on treating chemically polluted water, soil, or sediment. It allows users to define target media, compare treatment technologies, and address knowledge gaps in substance removal, transport, and fate to evaluate treatment effectiveness.

DSF Module: Search Substances

Problem: An environmental agency is concerned about PFAS contamination in agricultural soils because of the use of treated wastewater and sludge. They need to identify which PFAS are most relevant.

Solution: Using **Search Substances**, select agriculture under ‘sector of use’ and PFAS under ‘chemical class’ to generate a targeted list of relevant substances.

How the PROMISCES DSF helps: The **Search Substances** module allows users to explore PM(T) chemicals via sectors of use and chemical class to identify relevant substances for risk management and monitoring strategies.

DSF Module: Strategy Creation

Problem: A local government wants to create a water reuse zero-pollution strategy that considers social, financial and regulatory aspects, but needs guidance on where to start.

Solution: Using **Strategy Creation**, explore deliverables for guidance on co-creating strategies and takeaways from Case Study 3 on agricultural reuse.

How the PROMISCES DSF helps: Using the resources in the **Strategy Creation** module, decision-makers can combine insights from *Solution Assessment* module with real-world examples and to develop effective zero-pollution strategies.

PMT ASSESSMENT

Problem: An industrial site requests a permit for discharging wastewater containing unregulated substances, such as 1,4-dioxane. Authorities need to assess the permit request to protect the receiving water body.

Solution: Using **PMT Assessment**, search for 1,4-dioxane to obtain information on its P, M and T characteristics, as well as the other substances.

SEARCH SUBSTANCES

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TREATMENT

Problem: A water utility is considering a semi-closed water cycle to improve drinking water supply but needs to ensure that it can effectively remove PM(T) substances, including PFAS.

Solution: Select Route A in the **Solution Assessment - Treatment** module to explore treatment technologies tested for a semi-closed water cycle and a set of target PM(T) substances.

DIAGNOSIS

Problem: A water utility is updating their PFAS monitoring strategy but is worried that key hazardous substances are missing.

Solution: Use **Diagnosis** to check the monitored chemicals, such as perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA) and find structurally similar ones with equal or greater PM(T) risk. Then, use *Search Substances* for more details on these chemicals.

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How the PROMISCES DSF helps: The **Search Substances** module allows users to explore PM(T) chemicals via sectors of use and chemical class to identify relevant substances for risk management and monitoring strategies.

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DIAGNOSIS

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RISK ASSESSMENT

How the PROMISCES DSF helps: The **Solution Assessment - Risk Assessment** module compiles information on regulatory limits and health-based guideline values and provides PROMISCES-developed models to assist decision makers in implementing safe wastewater reuse.

PREVENTION

How the PROMISCES DSF helps: The **Solution Assessment - Prevention** module identifies where a substance is used and suggests safer alternatives or non-substitution measures like BATs or SSbD. Further, a link to the *PMT Assessment* module helps to identify whether the substance has P, M or T characteristics.

